

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE ECONOMIC SECURITY OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE BUSINESS ACTIVITY

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Abstract: After small business and private entrepreneurship activity has become the "driver" of the economy in our country, it is more than ever necessary to analyze the comprehensive development of this sector and, most importantly, the principles of its anti-crisis management, as well as the factors affecting its economic security. From this point of view, in this article, factors affecting business activity and its economic security are thoroughly analyzed, and conclusions and suggestions are presented at the end.

Key words: Small business, private entrepreneurship, economic security, fraud, risk.

From an economic point of view, small business represents a layer engaged in the activity of earning income by offering certain types of goods and services to the local market for exchange. Small business has its own characteristics, the ability to quickly adapt to the market, to produce quality products; able to meet the demand for goods and services necessary for the needs of the population in a relatively short period of time; relatively small amount of initial investment; the possibility of helping to create new jobs and solve the employment problem; direct participation of the business owner in the implementation of business activities, etc. The economic aspects and beneficial features of small business are covered as follows:

- small business - the front and source of income that uses labor for a large part of the population, the most flexible part of the labor market, which employs most of the labor resources who do not have sufficient qualifications and experience, who want a flexible working day. Women, young people who are looking for work for the first time, people with a low level of education and work experience are often the only ones who can find a job here. Being the main source of income not only for the majority of people engaged in this front, but also for their family members indicates that small business has become an important factor for the growth of national welfare;

- small entrepreneurship is a potentially effective tool for developing business and entrepreneurial skills among the population, increasing its level of adaptation to market relations. It enables citizens to own not only their own labor force, but also

their own property, including property intended for production, and is able to ensure the progressive development of the middle class-society, a social stratum interested in democracy and social stability. creates a basis for its formation;

- small business significantly increases the efficiency of the entire economy. He adapts to changes in consumer demand faster than anyone else, can change the specialty of his activity quickly and relatively easily in accordance with the fluctuations of the economic situation;

- small business improves the territorial structure of the economy. For an individual, doing a small business provides an opportunity to get busy and earn, to integrate work and personal life more holistically, and to demonstrate one's ability and talent.[1]

Secondly, in the process of globalization of the economy, competition in the world market will become stronger. In such conditions, it is the small business that requires more capital expenditure compared to large manufacturers, in addition to its compactness, it is able to quickly adapt to the necessary principles, the changing requirements of the market situation and the economic crises that occur from time to time, production has the ability to rapidly modernize its capacities. The conjuncture of consumer goods in the world market changes every 9 months on average. If we take this into account, it is clear how important small business and private entrepreneurship are in the consistent development of the country's economy. The establishment of networks supplying components and materials to large enterprises was encouraged. This allows solving the problem of production of import-substituting products in the industry and leads to an increase in the volume of exports of goods and technologies to the foreign market. The implemented measures ensure that the share of small business and private business entities in the total volume of products and services provided in our country grows steadily. This is an important factor in ensuring sustainable economic growth.

Since the years of independence, our country has been continuing to regularly support small business and private entrepreneurship on the way to a step-by-step transition to a market economy. If we look at statistical data, the number of registered small businesses and enterprises operating in the field of private entrepreneurship has increased from 213,643 to 488,936 in the last eight years, by almost 230 percent or 2.3 times.

One of the most important and main tasks of ensuring the country's economic security is monitoring the state of the economy, identifying threats and dangers in economic systems in time. At the same time, it is important to prepare management decisions on security as an organizational information technology system and

institution in the state management cycle. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the system of monitoring the state and dynamics of the country's economy and the level of its scientific-practical, methodological support. It is based on indicators in the assessment of a number of indicators and is mainly reflected in government scientific periodicals and analytical developments.[5] Through this, the government evaluates the situation at all levels: short-term (tactical), medium-term, long-term (strategic) and begins to prepare rational management decisions.

In conclusion, it can be said that the countries aiming for sustainable development in the conditions of the market economy should implement the following tasks in the near future:

- to support effective and competitive production and to stop obsolete production without prospects;
- development of economic infrastructures necessary for the implementation of structural changes;
- ensuring effective use of economic resources;
- preservation of the most valuable elements of the existing scientific and technical potential;
- to put an end to the deformation of the structure of the economy, to implement deep structural changes, to harmonize the structure of production with the demand capable of paying;
- acceleration of adaptation of enterprises to market conditions; - diversification of export potential;
- improvement of environmental safety.

It should be considered as an urgent task, of strategic importance, and an important issue.

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